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Is Success an Elusive Phenomenon for Working Women? : An Enquiry Suruchi Bhatia* and Gopa Bhardwaj**

Abstract

Empowerment is a value-laden, culturally-specific construct, its determinants with regard to women may vary with changes in social, religious, and cultural norms. In view of the nature of this construct, the present study makes a concise and unbiased attempt to identify, understand, analyse and interpret various determinants and trajectories of women empowerment in the Indian scenario. Qualitative data were gathered from primary (i.e. in-depth, semi-structured interviews of working women in positions of decision-making power within organisations; N = 30) and secondary (i.e. autobiographies and biographies of salient Indian women personalities; N = 7) sources which were then analysed and compared using content analysis. The findings of the study showed childhood socialisation, education, personality and motivation, career development, power and politics, and availability of support systems as being poignant themes that shape and explain the popular Indian narrative surrounding women empowerment. The themes so identified only go on to reiterate the critical role of empowerment in determining women's position in contemporary Indian society.

Keywords: women empowerment, personality, career development, power and politics

Women are often studied in comparison to the male standards (Davidson & Cooper 1987). The very step of comparison sets the male behaviour as the standard against which the female has to stand and prove herself. In many countries a few exceptional women have risen to the top and ruled with powerful strategies. There have also been some women who were brilliant teachers and able administrators, but their numbers are extremely meagre. Vast majorities were busy toiling, working hard for daily chores of routine activities and menial jobs as perceived by the male. This was perhaps due to the structure of the society where women occupied a subservient position irrespective of their occupational roles. As put forward by Gutek and Larwood (1987) that it is likely that women's career orientation will be different from men, it is not necessary that every study of women's career development involve comparison with men. They are born different, grow different, behave different. Hence, they need to be understood differently.

In this present study, the focus was primarily on and for women. The subjectivity induced by previous studies due to comparison with male performers was rendered as cliché. The subject matter of women's development has surfaced in a significant manner in the third world too. This is largely because women have participated in fulfilling economic and other needs through a demand and participation for equality in opportunity. Moreover, now-a-days women are increasingly putting through a convincing evidence of strong mindset for overcoming the very treatment they were meted out with, be it household or work-related.

In patriarchal societies, men have dominated with little recognition for the rights of women. The woman's basic job of housekeeping, bearing and raising children and processing the raw products obtained from hunt and farm, which although imperative for survival, but rarely given the credit it deserved. At best, there was a tacit acknowledgement that women discharged certain important functions, but they were deemed as secondary to what men did. Only a few generations separate the developed world from the time when women were neither permitted to vote or to enter most decision-making establishments or jobs requiring highly technical skills. D'Souza (1975) argues that in India as in other countries, there is a great discrepancy between the idealized concept of women and the real life situations in which women find themselves. In both the industrially advanced and less developed countries, women are burdened with cumulative inequalities as a result of socio-cultural and economic discriminatory practices which until recently have been taken for granted as though they were part of the immutable scheme of things established by nature. All over the world, women are denied equal access to opportunities for personal growth and social development in education, employment, marriage, family, profession and political life in comparison to males. Research found that 26% of middle managers were women whereas only 4% of senior managers were women (Kabasakal et al., 1994). Important career decisions are based often on social networks that exclude women and the long hours culture also works to women's disadvantage given their primary responsibilities towards home and family. Kabasakal et al. (2004)

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